

Structuring the Mediation Effect of Organizational Commitment between Abusive Supervision and Employees Work Performance

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Abstract

The topic of abusive supervision in the workplace is among the most studied subjects in different disciplines, including psychology, organizational behavior, and related fields. However, researchers and scholars ignore the mediation effect of organizational commitment in the relationship between abusive supervision and employee work performance. Moreover, there is a lack of studies undertaken on this issue in the public sector. This research data was collected in the Republic of Togo central government institutions and state-owned organizations, which are of particular importance and are filled with civil servants. The random sampling method was applied to collect the data from 214 respondents through structured survey questionnaires. The finding revealed that organizational commitment is mitigating the negative effect of abusive supervision on employees' performance. The results also showed that even though employees with normative commitment are most attached to the organization, they are less productive than individuals with affective and continuous commitment. Finally, the study concluded that civil servant with a strong organizational commitment doesn't show up on their supervisor's behavior but instead bear the character of "good citizenship."

Key words: Abusive Supervision, Organizational Commitment, Employees, Work Performance, Public Sector Institution.

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1. Introduction

Human Resources (HR) has a critical function and role in any organization because it is the most significant contributor to achieving its objectives (Armstrong, 2003; Hersey et al., 2007). Human resources in this study include all employees involved in the organization's operational activities. To achieve its goals, the organization depends heavily on the performance of its employees. However, support factors for creating excellent employee performance require an organizational commitment. Generally, employees who have a strong organizational commitment will grant all their skills and abilities to achieve their goals and perform better. Thereby, this could happen through the implementation of appropriate Human Resources Management (HRM) practices.

Additionally, the employee's interpersonal communication is necessary to maintain the motivation of the supervisor³ by explaining to subordinates about what to do, how to complete it, how well the subordinates are doing their job, and advise what subordinates can do to improve their work performance when their performance did not meet with the standards. Consequently, excellent interpersonal communication among supervisors and his/her subordinates will have a positive impact on their work performance.

Moreover, previous studies show that any damage caused to the employee through his/her supervisor's abusive supervision behavior will likely harm his/her work performance (Bowling & Michel, 2011; Martinko et al., 2013; Qian et al., 2017; Zellars et al., 2002a;). Furthermore, many scholars concluded that abusive supervision is negatively related to employee participation in a given organization. Meanwhile, other groups of scholars suggested that the increase of employee's organizational commitment provides a foundation for the emotional connection between an individual and his organization and thus increases his work performance (Cooper-Hakim & Viswesvaran, 2005; Dalal, 2005; Riketta, 2002; Tyll et al., 2020).

Although both links such as abusive supervision and employees' work performance and employee's organizational commitment and their work performance are well established by senior scholars, less attention has been paid to analyses how individual strong organizational commitment could mitigate the negative impact of the supervisor abusive supervision behavior. Therefore, aimed to be a theoretical contribution, this paper first sought to explore and model the precise mechanism by which abusive supervision affects employee work performance in public sector organizations. Second, the study addresses the mediation effect of the three types of organizational commitment: affective, continuous, and normative in the relationship between abusive supervision and employees' work performance. Hence, fostering a theoretical understanding of the mediation affecting individual organizational commitment in the relationship

³ Supervision in this study refers to control activities where control is an activity to determine what will be achieved with the organization (standard), how it will be implemented, to evaluate how it will be carried out and, if necessary, what corrective measures are required so that the implementation can proceed as planned, according to default standards

between abusive supervision and employees' work performance, these results are expected to be of practical value to organizations.

2. Literature Review and Theories

Relationship between abusive supervision and employee performance

In our decades, the issue of abusive supervision has received increasing attention in organizational management. Abusive supervision has adverse effects on the subordinate's physical and mental behavior resulting in a generally negative impact on the organization (Carlson et al., 2012). Although some organizational supervisors do not doubt the adverse effects of abusive supervision on employees' performance (Sulea et al., 2013, Thau et al., 2009), the question remains unknown why this supervision style persists in the workplace. One possible explanation is that supervision in organizations emphasizes discipline and authority (Pellegrini & Scandura, 2008), with supervisors tending to control the vast majority of valuable resources. In many organizations, employees must unquestionably respect or obey the orders requested by their supervisor, which leads employees of this organization to develop a higher tolerance for abusive supervision, leading to a predominance of this supervision style.

Abuse in itself is a stressful event that people face. Besides, since abusive supervision is defined as sustainable, dealing with the situation requires spending on resources. In turn, the lack of resources implies a reduced capacity to participate in constructive behaviors, such as Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCBs), and the lack of resources increases negative behaviors, such as Counterproductive work behavior (CWB) (Fox et al., 2001). With an estimated 13.6% (Fox et al., 2001), abusive supervision is an actual organizational and social problem. Hence, Supportive supervisors can provide information that clarifies job roles or suggests tasks that maximize the match between an employee's skills and job demands (Jokisaari & Nurmi, 2009). Consequently, abusive supervision harms the employee's work performance.

Hypothesis 1: Abusive Supervision has a negative and significant effect on employee performance.

Nevertheless, the background and psychological mechanisms for abusive supervision on civil servant work performance through organizational commitment are not well understood, especially in the public sector. Speaking of public sector organizations' critical goals, it is about achieving maximum employee performance and strengthening their commitment to the organization by improving their skills and abilities (Ergün et al., 2008). Thus, managers must demonstrate attitudes and behaviors to increase their employees' organizational commitment (Bagci & Yazici, 2013). Employees with a high organizational commitment are more involved in activities, produce more, work better in the organization, establish good relationships with other organization members, and have a higher level of job satisfaction than employees who have a lower level of organizational commitment.

Theoretical Perspectives

The theoretical framework in academic studies generally aims to clarify, predict, and understand phenomena and, in many cases, challenge existing knowledge within the limits of the critical limit hypothesis (Alexander, 1982). The theoretical framework is an arrangement that can support the theory of a research problem. The theory that explains why the issue of a study exists is familiar and described. Referring to this notion, research on the impact of abusive supervision on employee performance will analyze theories based on leadership, organizational performance, employee participation in decision-making, and employee engagement. Theories are applied as an analytical tool to recognize and clarify the issues related to the research topic and conceptual framework to guide the study in establishing research questions parallel to the collection data tool (Riede, Jokinen, Ruuskanen, & Farrall, 2014). Therefore, this study's broadest knowledge is based on contingent (situational) leadership and social exchange theories.

Effects of Employee's Management Practices According to the theory of contingency or situational leadership

The theory of contingency or situational leadership is one of the main leadership theories that emphasize a supervisor's decision-making. The theory developed by Hersey and Blanchard (1969) was known as life circle leadership theory, and later (1977), it changed its name to situational leadership theory. The theory proposes that supervisors choose the best course of action based on situational variables. The theory emphasizes that several factors affect the decision-making of the supervisor on a given issue. Factors such as motivation, competence, knowledge, beliefs, and the relationship between a supervisor and subordinate may affect the supervisor's supervision style (Graeff, 1983).

The theory highlights no single formula for supervision because the environment's internal and external dimensions require that a supervisor adopt a particular situation (Graeff, 1983). The supervisor's style must be changed to reflect the subordinates' developing maturity, which considers his/her inspiration and his/her ability to work. Therefore, depending on existing factors or circumstances, the supervisor would have more or less emphasis on the task he/she faced or the link between the supervisor and the subordinate. The situational leadership theory is that for the supervisor to be effective, he/she must be able to adapt to the situation (Mokdad et al., 2016). With this type of supervision, subordinates have played a fundamental role in the description of supervision. Although the theory of situational leadership is one of the best-known theories which has existed for several years and proved to be reliable, it has been discovered that there is little experimental evidence to support its ongoing use. However, it should not be completely discredited; and has provided a base of social interaction skills (Mokdad et al., 2016).

Effects of Employee's Management Practices According to the Theory of Social Exchange

The theory of social exchange (Blau, 1964) aims to explain the mechanisms that govern the exchange of specific resources, of a non-economic nature, between an entity (general administration) or a person (employer's representative or immediate supervisor) and, on the other hand, a person (employee) or a group of people (a work team). Often cited in sociology and organizational psychology researches, this theory helps to understand employees' decisions to compete or not in a practical way, to the excellent functioning of the organization in response to the exchange relations that they are experiencing at work based on the analyzes of social association processes (Leahy-Warren et al., 2012).

Numerous researchers, including Bishop, Scott, & Burroughs (2000), and Konovsky (2000), have shown that organizations are places of mutual social exchange that enhance their employees' organizational commitment more or less in the long term between employees and their employer or their supervisor. However, it depends on the trust that one of the parties demonstrates compliance with the other party (Sampson & Laub, 2005). According to Moulaert et al. (2011), people management practices that value people's contributions and lead to employees' investments can be seen as a sign of support and a manifestation of people's will. The organization has to establish an exchange relationship with others in the short or long term. Such kind of HRM practices appeared to have positive and lasting effects, particularly on critical attitudes, such as organizational commitment, leading to his/her intention to remain in the organization (Pinaridi et al., 2003, Meyer & Smith, 2000, Whitener, 2001), as well as on overall job satisfaction and work stress reduction (Lowe et al., 2000).

Repeated by immediate managers and supervisors, perceived as voluntary, authentic, and fair, they play the role of staff members, especially those who internalize the rule of reciprocity, the part of a moral obligation as a must to fulfill. It develops a positive attitude of commitment and motivational behavior towards the organization or team (Staves, Wayne, & Leopold (1997). As Martin (2005) emphasized in the declaration of principles that underpins its renewed commitment model, it depends on the employer and its representatives, through its resource management practices to provide staff with several critical psychological benefits, including feelings of support, justice, recognition, that employees may feel because of these management practices by the employer. The issue arises now is what the management practices are of people, which, according to recent research, prove to be the most promising to create favorable psychological conditions for staff members' appearance or reinforce positive attitudes and behaviors.

Effects of Employee's Management Practices on Organizational Commitment

Since Lawler's 1986 proposal for a model of HRM practices, described as either innovative or high-performance (Levitsky & Way, 2002), many researchers have begun to test their expected successes, both for employees as well as for organizational effectiveness (Barraud-Didier, Guerrero, & Igalens, 2003, Meyer & Smith, 2000, Hoshi, Tremblay, Féger, Carras, & Strick, 2005). The positive impacts of organizational commitment on staff emergence for feelings of justice, support,

and trust in the organization have been identified in several studies as mediating or moderating the effect of these management practices on an emotional commitment to the organization (Gutiérrez, Michalakos, Van Munster, & Blanc, 2013). With social exchanges and reciprocity, employees will be more inclined to develop a sense of attachment to their organization, work unit, mobilize more collectively, and be more motivated. An employee will, therefore, invest efforts to contribute to the success of his organization as he assesses that the organization provides an equivalent contribution to his/her relationship (Allen, Vincent, Alsop, Ismail-zadeh, & Flecker, 2003, and Eisenberger, Armeli, Rexwinkel, Lynch, & Rhoades, 2001). Cardona, Lawrence, & Bentler (2004) have established that, contrary to social exchanges based on socio-emotional resources, transfers based mainly on economic contributions are not positively related to "good citizen" behaviors and organizational structure.

Further, some studies have examined individual differences in adherence to the reciprocity standard, postulated by Gouldner as a universal standard. In this respect, Eisenberger et al. (2001) show that adherence to the reciprocity standard accentuates employee's willingness to perform their tasks and get involved in the organization by reacting to their needs. His finding illustrates that employees who firmly adhere to the reciprocity standard are more likely to feel a moral debt to their organization, acknowledge the excellent treatment they receive, and dispel this feeling of royalty by deciding how to invest efforts to maintain and improve the functioning of the organization.

In summary, the theory of social exchange sheds light on why an organization that acts for its employees' good generates a strong organizational commitment to return the favor by enhancing their performance (Levine et al., 2006, Guerrero & Herrbach, 2008). In contrast, Saks & Ashforth (1997) and Zellars et al. (2002) et al. concluded their studies that abusive supervision was identified, leading to low performance (Tepper, 2000). Therefore, the proposed research model was applied to analyze how the employee's strong organizational commitment (affective, normative, and continuance) could mitigate the negative impact of abusive supervision on the employees' work performance.

Figure 1: Theoretical framework

Research Model (by the author)

The implication of Employees Organizational Commitment

Nowadays, organizations expect their employees to put forth more effort, be motivated, and take the initiative. The organization's success depends on how it improves its employees' skills and encourages its employees to commit to the organization (Belli & Ekici, 2012). One of the most critical business objectives is obtaining maximum yield from employees and increasing their commitment to the organization by enhancing their abilities and skills (Özler & Atalay, 2011). Thus, the managers need to exhibit attitudes and behaviors to increase employees' organizational commitment levels to increase employees' organizational commitment levels (Bağcı, 2013). It is seen that employees who have higher-level organizational commitment participate in organizations and production more, perform better in the organization, build good relationships with other members of the organization, and have higher work satisfaction levels, concerning the ones who have a lower-level organizational commitment (Özler & Atalay, 2011).

Individuals with a strong affective commitment are those employees with a secure emotional attachment, identification, and involvement in this organization. Identification happens when the employees' values are congruent with the organization's importance when it internalizes its values and assumes its objectives (Ghaley et al., 2018). An affective commitment that emotionally attaches people to the organization and ensures their happiness from being a member arises from the agreement between the individual and organizational values (Durna & Veysel, 2011). In general, people retained in the organization with a strong affective commitment behave like this not because they are required to keep in the organization but because they want to remain in the organization and work to achieve its goals (Colakoglu et al., 2010). However, employees with a strong desire to remain in the organization strive to fulfill their duties according to its required standards and do not judge their organization, relying on their supervisor's abusive behavior.

Hypothesis 2: Affective commitment is mediating the relationship between abusive supervision and employee performance.

The strong continuance commitment refers to "recognizing costs associated with the departure from the organization." This organization of this type of commitment was inspired by the theory of "side-bet" (H. S. Becker, 1960). The employees calculate their organization's investments, what they gain if they retain their membership, and what to lose if they leave the organization. The employees develop this type of commitment due to the lack of alternative employment (Zaharia et al., 2013). When an employee notices that leaving the organization has a higher

cost than remaining in that organization, the employee will stay in that organization just because he/she requires this (Akar, 2015). In this type of commitment, it is thought that emotions play a little role in organizational commitment. There are several individual and organizational factors during the formation of an employee's continuance commitment. It is possible to list the factors that influence continuance commitment: abilities, education, change of location, personal investment, pension liability, and society and other options (Bozkurt & İrfan, 2013). It also implied that the individual with a strong need to stay in the organization tends to develop a right work attitude that aligns with the culture of the organization while improving their performance (A. Cohen, 1996); hence, they display the attitudes and behaviors of good citizenship and their supervisor abusive behavior do not affect their work performance.

Hypothesis 3: Normative Commitment mediates the relationship between abusive supervision and employee performance.

The third and last concept is the normative commitment related to an employee's obligation to stay with the organization. Its influenced by social norms on whether people should remain committed to their organization. It is likely to develop as a feeling of reciprocation when the employee has a positive experience of their organization (Mitchell et al., 2012). Normative commitment is the organizational commitment's responsibility and ethical dimensions and reflects employees' liability feelings concerning retaining in the organization. Employee organizational commitment depends on the employee's social responsibility consciousness and his/her perception to remain in the organization as a duty. This type of commitment comes out when an employee considers retaining in the organization as correct. It represents a different standpoint for organizational commitment than the other two commitment types (Bozkurt & İrfan, 2013). Therefore, employees who have a moral obligation to retain in the organization will consequently strive to upgrade their performance to fulfill their needs (Cohen, 1996). However, they tend not to judge their organization base on their supervisor's abusive behavior.

Hypothesis 4: Continuance Commitment mediates the relationship between abusive supervision and employee performance.

Comparing the three types of organizational commitment, A. Cohen (1996) concluded that employees with strong affective commitment want to remain in the organization. After all, they want to continue working for the organization leading it to achieve its goal, individuals with strong continuance commitment since they want to work for the organization to contribute for its wellbeing, and those with strong normative commitment feel they ought to do so that the organization remain on track. In other words, this subject is evaluated in "desire" (affective), "need" (continuance), and "liability" (normative) (Durna & Veysel, 2011). Although

common to these different approaches is the link between employee and their organization, which decreases the likelihood of turnover, it is clear that the nature of these links influences employees' work performances.

3. Research Methodology

Existing literature showed a lack of empirical research in developing countries public sector HRM practices. However, this is not because researchers and scholars excluded this field, instead the barriers to access the information. The study data collection process lasted for three (3) months (the second trimester of 2019) because of the administrative requirements and procedure of getting permission to conduct a data collection survey in public institutions. The demand for data collection was rejected once and finally granted on the second demand at the Togolese institution of scholarship and internship management under the ministry of high education and research, which has the mandate to deliver a permission letter for data collection in the public sector. In the second stage in each institution, the potential respondents requested a permission letter from their hierarchy before participating in the survey. Moreover, some potential participants asked for financial compensation before filling the questionnaire.

The two letters of permission received, joined with a cover letter that clarified the study's purpose, were attached to the questionnaires and then sent to the randomly designated respondent to complete the survey themselves and assist us by asking their colleagues and employees to fill it return to us. Participants were requested to fill the questionnaires anonymously, and the probability random sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents.

The study population was the employees working in the Republic of Togo public organizations. The selected organizations are ministries, public universities, state-owned banking, state-owned mobile phone companies, local government members (municipality), autonomous organizations, and semi-governmental companies. The access to these organizations was based on personal contacts and suggestions from the Togolese institution of scholarship and internship management

A total of 214 filled questionnaires were returned to us out of 300 distributed. Among the 214, 74 were from the ministries, 27 from public university administrative staffs, 23 from State-owned banks, 19 from state-owned mobile phone companies, 52 from municipalities, and 19 from the autonomous and semi-governmental organizations". The reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's alpha coefficient = .79 base on the overall items to check the questionnaire's internal coherence of scale elements. Table 1 in the appendix presents the study participant background statistics.

Since the study applied for cross-sectional design, which consists of collecting the study data at a given time (the second trimester of 2019) on a random sample of the Togolese civil servant and aimed to analyze the HRM practice that is

happening in the Togolese public sector, it does not allow us any statistical inference or generalization of our conclusions outside the Study Universe.

Dependent Variable: Employee Work Performance

There is no unanimity in the analysis of performance phenomena, and that most studies suffer from a lack of proper reflection on the concept of individual performance at work (Charles-Pauvers et al., 2007). However, several authors have tried to define individual performance in the workplace. For Shustorovich (1992:704), own work performance is defined as "a set of behaviors or actions relevant to organizational goals and which can be measured in terms of competency levels and contributions to goals." For Motii & Chati (203), it is "the total value expected by the organization of discrete behavioral episodes performed by an individual over a while." Beyond this definition, several studies have proposed a multifactorial model of the nature of job performance behavior.

Three approaches dominate the literature on HRM and performance relationships. The first qualification as a universalist (Delery & Doty, 1996) shows that "good HRM practices" can positively affect organizations. It has excellent echoes in the scientific community (Tremblay, 2000) and has been validated through several functional empirical studies (Delery & Doty, 1996; Huselid, Jackson, & Schuler, 1997).

The second, approaching contingency, slightly the first nuance, is suggesting that HRM practices, to be effective, must be aligned with other contingency factors in the organization (Delery & Doty, 1996; Schuler & Jackson, 1987) and more accurately with its strategy.

The third configuration approach focuses on highlighting the set of HRM practices rather than specific methods. According to this latter approach, HRM practices will have a synergistic (mutually reinforcing) effect. This synergistic effect, adding to their interaction with strategy, will lead to better organizational performance (Arthur, 1994). Tremblay (2000), in the Arsan, Guest, Gagnadoux, & Broyer, (1997), explains that this model is not rich enough in terms of information to justify why HRM policies and practices are related to better organizational performance; therefore, there is the need to take into account interacting variables such as organizational commitment components.

Mediation Variable: Organizational commitment

The literature has made it possible to identify certain mediation variables, including affective commitment (M1), normative commitment (M2), and continuous commitment (M3), that have an essential influence on employee work performance. These variables were included in the statistic process model 4 (Hayes, 2017) to check how they can mitigate the negative effect of the independent variable (abusive supervision) on the dependent variable (employee work performance).

Employee's organizational commitment, the paper relied on Meyer and Allen, (1991) model that he developed to measure the three components of the individual, organizational commitment such as affective commitment, normative

commitment, and continuous commitment, which have had contributed independently to the prediction of work activity and work behavior. However, this model (the three components of commitment) has been revised and improved, and its final version is presented in Table 1.

Table 2. the three-component model of commitment

Affective Commitment	1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.
	2. I feel as if this organization's problems are my own.
	3. I do not feel a strong sense of "belonging" to my organization.
	4. I do not feel "emotionally attached" to this organization.
	5. I do not feel like "part of the family" at my organization.
	6. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.
Continuance commitment	7. Right now, staying with my organization is a matter of necessity as much as desired.
	8. It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now, even if I wanted to.
	9. Too much of my life will be disrupted if I decide to leave my organization now.
	10. I feel that I have too few options to consider leaving this organization.
	11. If I had not already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.
	12. One of the few negative consequences of leaving this organization would be the scarcity of available alternatives.
Normative commitment	13. I do not feel any obligation to remain with my current employer.
	14. Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.
	15. I would feel guilty if I left my organization now.
	16. This organization deserves my loyalty.
	17. I would not leave my organization right now because I have a sense of obligation to the people in it.
	18. I owe a great deal to my organization.

Source: Meyer, Allen, and Smith, 1993.

Independent Variable: Abusive Supervision

As previously defined, abusive supervision is a managerial relationship interspersed with angry words or gestures. In other terms, abusive supervision refers to subordinates' perceptions about the level of adoption of hostile words or behavior by supervisors (Tepper, 2000). Therefore, this oversight is a hierarchical abuse that manifests itself in all forms of non-physical violence at work or deliberate attempts to cause harm. i.e., abusive supervision refers to the supervisor's verbal abuse expressed through words, not Physical violence, manifested through gestures.

4. Results and Discussions

Statistics analysis was undertaken to determine whether the association between the response and each term in the model is statistically significant and test the research hypothesis by applying multiple regression analysis and linear regression with process macro model 4. This two-dimensional correlation analysis does not determine the mediation effect of organizational commitment between

abusive supervision and employee work performance but a hierarchical regression analysis to find the most critical organizational commitment based on theory.

Table 3: Variable that contributes to the model (Coefficients^a); the Moderation Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	.95 Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.833	.280		6.554	.000	1.283	2.383
Abusive Supervision	.463	.069	.327	6.743	.000	.328	.598
2 (Constant)	.977	.310		3.152	.002	.367	1.586
Abusive Supervision	.319	.071	.225	4.496	.000	.180	.459
Affective Commitment	.408	.073	.280	5.584	.000	.265	.552
3 (Constant)	.956	.310		3.082	.002	.346	1.565
Abusive Supervision	.300	.073	.211	4.129	.000	.157	.442
Affective Commitment	.375	.078	.257	4.819	.000	.222	.528
Normative Commitment	.072	.057	.067	1.265	.207	-.040	.184
4 (Constant)	.299	.314		.951	.342	-.319	.917
Abusive Supervision	.185	.072	.131	2.581	.010	.044	.326
Affective Commitment	.208	.079	.143	2.638	.009	.053	.363
Normative Commitment	.019	.055	.017	.343	.732	-.089	.127
Continuance Commitment	.501	.081	.334	6.167	.000	.341	.661

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

Source: data field 2019

Looking at the p-value of the t-test of all predictors in models 1, 2, 3, and 4, we can see that each variable contributes to the model, but normative commitment does not. Consequently, the interconnection among the response and the variable in the models is statistically significant compared to 5%, the p-value to access the null hypothesis except "Normative Commitment." In general, employees with normative commitment are less binding, and as a result, normative commitment is pointed out as weaker than affective commitment and continuance commitment. Therefore, even though employees with normative commitment are usually most attached to the organization (J. P. Meyer & Parfyonova, 2010), their work performance is still less than others.

This finding is consistent with the main conclusions of the previous studies. Given that the earlier conclusions are mainly based on studies focused on the private sector, we conclude that the correlation between variables related to the organizational commitment in the Togolese public sector is similar to that found in other sectors. As a result, the Togolese public sector does not seem particularly unusual. However, the intensity of the correlation with normative commitment is not significant, which agrees with the previous conclusions. Additionally, the similarities found between this study's findings in the public sector and prior studies using the three components of organizational commitment show that the main antecedents of organizational commitment in the private and public sectors are not much different. Hence, the public sector can learn more about organizational

commitment by looking at studies in the private sector, including how it affects staff involvement. In this regard, the importance of HRM techniques that can contribute to organizational support (Bush & Meyer, 2002) and self-confidence (Gould-Williams & Davies, 2005) are points of interest for managers.

Table 4: Total, Direct, and Indirect effect (the mediation analysis)

total effect of X on Y	c	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c_ps	c_cs
	.4633	.0727	6.3690	.00	.3203	.6064	.4705	.3269
direct effect of X on Y	c'	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c_ps	c_cs
M ₁ = Affective Commitment	.3192	.0797	4.0037	.00	.1624	.4759	.3241	.2252
indirect effect of X on Y	(a.b)	SE	a	t _a	P _a	b	t _b	P _b
M ₁ = Affective Commitment	.1442	.0365	.3531	7.0165	.0000	.4083	5.3443	.0000
direct effect of X on Y	c'	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c_ps	c_cs
M ₂ = Normative Commitment	.3912	.0794	4.9285	.00	.2351	.5473	.3972	.2760
indirect effect of X on Y	(a.b)	SE	a	t _a	P _a	b	t _b	P _b
M ₂ = Normative Commitment	.0721	.0284	.4346	6.6126	.0000	.1660	2.8959	.0040
direct effect of X on Y	c'	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI	c_ps	c_cs
M ₃ = Continuance Commitment	.2294	.0816	2.8106	.0052	.0689	.3898	.2329	.1618
indirect effect of X on Y	(a.b)	SE	a	t _a	P _a	b	t _b	P _b
M ₃ = Continuance Commitment	.2340	.0428	.3922	8.0292	.0000	.5966	7.9569	.0000

Y: Employees Organizational Performance, X: Abusive Supervision,
M₁: Affective Commitment, M₂: Normative Commitment, and M₃: Continuance Commitment
Source: data field 2019

To check how abusive supervision influences employees' performance through organizational commitment, process analysis was applied to compute the independent variable's direct, indirect, and total effect (ID) on the dependent variable (DV).

The direct and indirect effect of abusive supervision through affective commitment on individual performance, the results have shown that the direct effect (c' = .3192) is greater than the indirect effect (a.b = .1442). That means that individuals with affective commitment are those with a strong feeling and attachment to the organization and are always ready to fulfill the need and requirement (Kimura, 2013 (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Consequently, individuals with affective commitment have a strong desire to stay in the organization, strictly focus on their unit goals, vision, and mission, Meyer et al., 2002), pay respect to their supervisor and abide by the organization rules and work regulations and less likely to resign even though under the pressure of their supervisor.

This finding is supporting existing literature including Mathieu & Zajac (1990); Ryan, Althoff, Whitlow, & Cohen (2000); D. B. Meyer & Pooley, (2002);

and Boyd, Boyd, & Vandenberghe (2004), which showed that employee with affective commitment reduces intention to leave the organization. The organizational work code that defines employees' job desk acknowledges, accepts, and considers employees' perspectives by describing the reasons behind every decision. Every request, every new procedure, or regulation contributes significantly to increasing employees' affective commitment and enhancing their work performance. Bush & Meyer (2002) added that employees who desire to remain in the organization would have more desire to contribute to their goals. In contrast, those who stay in the organization for one obligation or another or their financial needs will have -less will.

Likewise, the direct effect ($c' = .3912$) is greater than the indirect effect ($a.b = .0721$) for abusive supervision toward employees' normative commitment on their performance. Also, the coefficient that defines the causal relationship between employee's normative commitment and abusive Supervision (M/X) with the p-value for ta-test: $6.6126 = .000$ is significant; hence the p-value for tb-test: $2.8959 = .0040$ for the weight between abusive supervision and normative commitment (X/M) is also significant. As a result, since the path from X to Y after introducing the mediator variable (direct effect) is less than the total effect, it is concluded that there is a partial mediation effect. Hence, employees with normative commitment feel obligated to their organization, even if they are not satisfied with the function or even want to look for better opportunities. They think they have to stay with their organization because it is the right thing (Sow, Anthony, & Berete, 2016; Balassiano & Salles, 2012). Another group of researchers and scholars such as Jaros (1997); Bush & Meyer (2002); Paillé, (2004); El Akremi, Ameer, & Toulouse, (2005) finding aligned with our finding which has shown that employees with normative commitment are negatively correlated with intention to leave the organization. This perspective is characteristic of respecting the social conventions that an individual fosters in connection with his/her organization Paillé, (2004); Daskalopoulou et al., (2015). It can also be translated into compliance with psychological contracts and organizational justice.

For the continuance commitment, there is a gap between direct effect to indirect effect, i.e., the indirect effect ($a.b = .2340$) is greater than the direct effect ($c' = .2294$), which means that individuals with continuance commitment and their work performance are inevitably linked, (Khan et al., 2016). In addition, the p-values for ta-test: $8.0292 = .000$ and tb-test: $7.9569 = .000$ are significant. Hence, employees with continuance commitment agree to work under their supervisor's pressure to add the additional requirement and fulfill the organization's goal. Besides, the finding shows that employees with continuous commitment and their decision to improve their work performance are not related to psychological effects. These findings aligned with the conclusion of Fortin et al., (2005), who concluded that with invested efforts and accumulated profits, it becomes difficult for employees to leave the organization, thereby arousing the desire to continue individual / organizational relationships. A study by El Akremi et al.)2005) shows that the calculated involvement is negatively related to intention to leave the organization.

Moreover, individual characteristics, like professional characteristics, only have a weak effect on employee performance. Independence and doing interesting work also have relatively weak effects. The same applies to organizational features, which only have a weak and insignificant influence. The most important observation concerns that the effect of satisfaction concerning HRM effect is the third most important among the variables related to history. High satisfaction with HRM is associated with higher organizational commitment. Once again, this shows that human resource (HR) policies well received by affected employees will positively influence their performance. Additionally, the findings show a strong sectoral influence because workers in the public sector have commitments to set standards that are slightly higher than those of other private-sector workers without performance incentives.

To sum it up, the finding shows that human resource management (HSM) practice in the Republic of Togo determines the efficient movement of people permitted to be encouraged and committed. The progress that conditions the workforce to establish with certainty the meaning of HRM in picking only for this changed their movements to display their own relatives' voices. Trudel et al.) 2005) concluded that this practice influenced employee organizational commitment. Additionally, according to the existing literature, organizational commitment components appear to be a factor that affects employee work performance (Chevrier et al., 2000; Lawler, 1993). Our results empowered these by confirming that strong organizational commitment reduces abusive supervision's negative effect on employee work performance. Hence, the stronger is employee organizational commitment; the higher probability is to mitigate abusive supervision's negative effect on the employee.

5. Conclusions

The finding sheds light that employee with strong organizational commitment who experienced abusive supervision still have a strong will to give their best to fulfill the organization's needs. What made the finding of this study unique is that the research was undertaken in the public sector. A civil servant's opinion on their supervisor's behavior regarding the common national goodwill task probably differs from those in the private sector; hence, "good citizenship." Good citizenship in this study refers to the individual (civil servant) with strong organizational commitment who experiences abusive supervision but takes it as a personal character of their supervisor and does not judge the organization. Therefore, the finding of this quest far be in contradiction with existing kinds of literature on the effect of abusive supervision in the workplace, such as Fakhar (2014); Gopalkrishnan (2013); Zellars et al. (2002); M. S. Mitchell & Ambrose (2007) and others but bring a new contribution in the field.

Besides, our conclusions about normative commitment make sense compared to other studies' findings, attributed to the lack of Public Service Motivation (PSM) among Togolese public sector workers. If normative commitment implies a sense of obligation, this is similar to PSM's perception, which considers it to indicate a "call" or "sense of duty (Houston, 2000). Although

Rainey & Steinbauer (1999) clearly distinguish between commitment to organizational mission and commitment to public goals served by the organization, one can recognize as an assumption that normative commitment has a different meaning in the public sector and the private sector because of the presence of PSM. It seems less clear concerning affective and continuous commitment because the purpose is less closely related to the PSM. This reasoning will explain the difference between our conclusions about normative commitment and those from other studies.

Still, the research suggests additional studies to be carried out that will include measures of organizational commitment and motivation for public service. Besides, the study also suggests future works aiming to compare civil servants' and private workers' opinions regarding the issue therein. Evermore, the research suggests a future quest on the relationship between abusive supervision and individual performance through the mediation of organizational commitment with the moderator factor as organizational judgment. The organizational culture is a subset of introverted myths and rituals that allow individuals to adapt to the organization's overall structure (Riveline, 1993), thus appearing to be a critical factor in HRM and related studies that seek to understand the effect of abusive supervision on employees work performance. However, the current paper mainly focused on the effect of the three organizational commitment components in the relationship between supervisor abusive supervision behavior and employees' work performance has made an exception. Therefore, it is suggested that further studies on the issue raised in this paper should consider organizational culture in its analysis”.

Study Limitation

However, this study has certain limitations. Since the study was conducted in a few organizations, the results obtained cannot be generalized to other organizations in the same activity sector and even less for other activity sectors. The fact that the various employee working on different job categories in the organization concerned is also not represented in our sample do not allow us to generalize the survey results. The second limitation, which affects the internal validity of our findings, relates to the fact that all variables are measured simultaneously from one source (employee) through a self-administered questionnaire, which can thus contribute to the risk of general variance errors, which tends to exert an upward influence on the relationship found between our variables.

Another limit is related to the nature of the variable being measured; they are based on employee perceptions, creating a risk of social desires. Thus, as Duguay et al. (2010) point out, the variables investigated in this study are "very sensitive elements and may have been influenced by participants' interpretations of possible data use," and this is independent of the commitment made in connection with anonymity in processing and yield returns. However, it is employee perceptions that form the basis of research because if people's management practices, called high performance (Levitsky & Way, 2002) do exist within an organization but are not felt by employees, they will not create feelings of fairness,

support and organizational commitment needed for a lasting work relationship. The fourth limit refers to the presence of upside-down goods in our measuring instruments. As Levine et al.)2006) have noted in their research using the same measurement scale, inverted items must be removed after confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results are included in appendices (table 5 & 6), presenting a weak saturation coefficient. We share Quenneville's opinion on this matter, stating, "for reasons that might be related to lack of attention or misunderstanding" (Levine et al., 2006), many of our respondents' misinterpreted statements expressed negatively. The fifth significant limitation arises from this study's cross-sectional design, making it difficult to investigate causality and the absence of a mediating evaluating test following the procedure recommended by Rhoades, Eisenberger, & Armeli,)2001).

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Appendix A; Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Gender	214	1	2	1.26	.437
Age	214	1	5	1.66	.902
Experience (years):	214	1	5	2.70	1.142
Level of Education	214	1	4	2.27	.682
Valid N (listwise)	214				

Source: data field 2019

Appendix B; Table 5: Rotated Component Matrix ^a (Factor Analysis Results)

	1	2	3	4	5
Q1	.677	-.145	-.003	-.021	.010
Q3	.672	-.194	-.055	-.122	-.174
Q4	.648	.059	.004	.078	-.088
Q2	.646	.034	.032	.134	-.071
Q5	.644	-.015	-.088	.035	.011
Q6	.628	.097	.039	.078	-.105
Q7	-.053	.812	-.034	-.056	-.072
Q11	.017	.811	.126	.026	-.081
Q9	.032	.793	.031	-.038	.026
Q10	-.031	.771	.098	.163	-.061
Q8	-.001	.744	.091	-.083	.024
Q12	.022	.738	.120	.162	-.049
Q16	.025	.252	.712	.150	.062
Q14	.104	.087	.699	.005	-.098
Q17	-.047	.262	.687	.052	-.005
Q13	.189	.319	.633	-.002	.015
Q15	.037	.264	.605	.336	-.107
Q18	-.042	.089	.605	.343	.007
Q22	.064	.168	.142	.665	.034
Q20	.109	.121	.214	.656	-.037
Q19	.069	.132	.178	.584	-.082
Q21	-.045	.051	.192	.541	.057

Q23	.257	-.031	.306	.523	.004
Q25	-.177	.028	-.032	-.057	.589
Q26	-.136	-.081	-.177	.037	.547
Q24	.114	-.101	.104	-.110	.540
Q27	-.235	.087	-.154	-.014	.525
Q28	.298	-.175	.080	-.182	.495
Q30	.302	-.146	.072	-.043	.487
Q31	.337	.124	-.176	.040	.476

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 7 iterations.

Appendix C; Tabel 6: Model Fit Indices (*Overall Model Fit*)

indices	Cut-off-Value	Results	conclusion
Goodness of Fit Indices (GFI)	$0,85 \leq \text{GFI} < 0,90$	0,807	Marginal fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	$\geq 0,90$	0,912	Good fit
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	$\geq 0,90$	0,917	Good fit
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	$0,80 \leq \text{NFI} < 0,90$	0,845	Marginal fit
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	$\leq 0,08$	0,045	Good fit
Root Mean Square Residual (RMSR)	$\leq 0,1$	0,037	Good fit

Source: data field 2019